

BUILDING AN APPROPRIATE RECYCLING SYSTEM FOR UZBEKISTAN

Khilola Sultonova

Hitotsubashi University, JAPAN

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***Abstract.** Uzbekistan's rapid population growth and economic development have significantly increased municipal solid waste generation, creating a need for effective waste management strategies. This study evaluates the waste recycling system in Tashkent by analyzing waste flow, stakeholder roles, and systemic inefficiencies. Using data from the ADB's 2012 evaluation, Maxsustrans databases, semi-structured interviews, and field observations, the study found that the 2017 recycling rate was lower than prior estimates, with most recycling operations functioning at a basic, informal level. Approximately 180 tons of recyclable waste are processed daily through 110 recycling markets, yet weak enforcement of government policies hinders system efficiency.*

The study highlights the gaps in policy implementation and the need for structured, sustainable recycling mechanisms. These findings provide valuable insights for policymakers and urban planners, offering guidance on improving policy enforcement and integrating formal recycling systems into Tashkent's waste management framework. During my current PhD research, I intend to extend this study by utilizing the most recent data available, providing a comprehensive and updated assessment of Tashkent's waste recycling system. This will allow for a more accurate understanding of the current state of recycling in Tashkent and identify potential areas for improvement.

Keywords: *Municipal solid waste management; Recycling system; Uzbekistan*

1. Introduction

My first exposure to the idea of recycling municipal waste occurred in 2011. I was employed as a translator for Japanese business representatives who had come to Uzbekistan to introduce products and services offered by their companies. One of these

companies was in the recycling business, and as I translated this company's discussions, I became very interested in the possibilities of recycling. I learned that the garbage we were disposing of in landfills was actually a valuable resource, and we were destroying material that could be transformed into other products. That experience led to my interest in learning more about waste recycling systems and this research into the possibilities for introducing those systems to Uzbekistan.

Over the past decades, many developing countries, including Uzbekistan, have been facing rapid population growth and economic development, which has also created rapid growth in solid waste generation. Urbanization and population growth accompanied by increasing gross domestic product (GDP) and a higher standard of living are the key reasons behind the magnitude of the growth in total waste generation (Linzner and Salhofer, 2014; Batool et al., 2008).

As waste generation is linked to economic growth, the problem of how to develop effective waste strategies is one that all governments face at same point. In this respect, developing countries have the advantage of learning from the experiences of developed countries that have experienced these problems earlier.

Municipalities, usually responsible for waste management in the cities, have the challenge to provide an effective and efficient system to the inhabitants. However, they often face problems beyond the ability of the municipal authority to tackle (Sujauddin, 2008) mainly due to lack of organization, financial resources, complexity and system multi dimensionality (Burntley, 2007).

It has been reported that collection, transfer and transport practices are affected by improper bin collection systems, poor route planning, lack of information about collection schedule (Hazra and Goel, 2009), insufficient infrastructure (Moghadam, 2009), poor roads and number of vehicles for waste collection (Henry, 2006).

Even some countries have placed recycling at the top of their waste management priorities, the low cost of landfill and the availability of land make recycling programs infeasible, uneconomical and unachievable (Jasem M. 2006)

The research literature is extensive and examines several methods for achieving effective waste management strategies in the cases of different countries. However, to

our knowledge, few studies have been conducted in Central Asia, or particularly in Uzbekistan. This research is thus a preliminary attempt to identify the current waste management and recycling system in Uzbekistan. The objective of this study is to determine the current waste amount flow and direction, stakeholders' action and behavior that have a role in the waste management process, and to analyze influential factors on the recycling system in capital Tashkent city.

The study is organized as follows. First section, we start by taking a brief look at the socio-economic background of the research area and the characterizations of solid waste management system in Uzbekistan. Essential waste management assessments and information utilized in this chapter have been sourced from the ADB solid waste management improvement project's evaluation and Maxsustrans databases. Here, we tried to introduce overview of the existing solid waste management system in the capital Tashkent city. Next, we provide a case study analysis and we will conduct the research survey based on the semi-interviews. Through the field survey results, we will determine the current problems and challenges of the recycling system in Tashkent city. In the discussion part, we will examine data of the estimations from SWIMP (2012) with the actual data (2017), and assess the waste recycling system in the city. Finally, conclusions and policy recommendations are presented at the end of study

2. Background

Located in the heartland of Central Asia, the Republic of Uzbekistan sits at the crossroads of the ancient Eurasian trade routes. The world's only doubly landlocked territory and covering 448,978km². It is a dry continental climate of low precipitation, hot summers and cold winters. Uzbekistan shares borders with Kazakhstan to the north and west, the Kyrgyz Republic and Tajikistan to the east, and Turkmenistan and Afghanistan to the south (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map of Uzbekistan

Source: ADB Uzbekistan Fact Sheet 2012

Uzbekistan consists of fertile river valleys surrounded by vast plains and mountain ranges. It has a wealth of natural resources including natural gas, minerals such as gold, uranium, potassium; and vibrant agriculture, most notably, the growing of cotton.

If we consider the history of statistical data on the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it was 4.6 million people in 1926 (Figure 2). However, the recent population of Uzbekistan reached to about 32.1 million in 2017, growing 1.7% annually from 2014 to 2016, Uzbekistan is the most populous nation in Central Asia, with 50,6% of the total population urban as recently as 2017. Although provinces vary significantly in population density, most people live in the eastern, southern and central-western parts of the country. Vast areas of central, northern and western Uzbekistan have extremely sparse populations.

Uzbekistan has the second largest economy in Central Asia with a per capita gross national income of \$2,220, and gross domestic growth rate was 7,8% in 2016.

Figure 2: Number of resident population of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Source: The state committee of the republic of Uzbekistan on statistics

Increasing population levels, economic growth, rapid urbanization and the rise in community living standards have greatly accelerated the municipal solid waste generation rate in Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan generates over 12,000 tons of municipal solid waste (MSW) daily, or over 4 million tons annually and this is expected to accelerate to over 7 million tons per year by 2030, cumulatively generating from 2013 to 2030 about 100 million tons of MSW.

Tashkent the most urban city of Uzbekistan faced the serious problems in its waste management problems system. Municipality is usually responsible for waste management in this city. The government of Uzbekistan has applied for a loan from the Asian Development (ADB) for the development and improvement of Solid Waste Management (SWM) system of capital city Tashkent in February 2014. The loan reference number and project title is L3067- UZB: Solid Waste Management Improvement Project (SWMIP). The project aims to provide an improved SWM system and upgrade urban infrastructure and services in the capital city Tashkent. The project will develop a sanitary landfill that meets international standards, rehabilitate transfer stations, and modernize the waste collection and transfer fleet. Monitoring of this project started since 2011. SWMIP assessed the Tashkent's solid waste management system and evaluated waste generation indicators through carrying several surveys. According to the project estimations, Tashkent generates 1,843 ton solid waste (including household and commercial waste) per day. From this waste, 1,567 ton goes to the landfill site to dispose. Moreover, project estimates waste

recycling rate as 15% for 2017 (Table 1).

Table 1: ADB Uzbekistan Solid Waste Management Investment Project Estimation

	Year	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
A	Tashkent City Population	2,319, 465	2,342, 660	2,366, 086	2,389, 747	2,413, 645	2,437, 781
B	Waste Generation per capita kg per day	0.56	0.56	0.57	0.57	0.58	0.58
C=A*B	Total Household Waste Generated per day/ton	1,288	1,314	1,341	1,368	1,395	1,423
D	Net Household Waste to Landfill ton	1,224	1,249	1,247	1,204	1,186	1,210
E	Commercial Waste Generation per day/ton	400	404	408.04	412.12	416.24	420.4
F	Net Commercial Waste to Landfill tons	380	384	379	363	354	357
G=C+E	Total Waste Generation per	1,688	1,718	1,749	1,780	1,811	1,843

	day/ton						
H	Total Waste to Landfill per day/ton	1,604	1,633	1,626	1,567	1,540	1,567
I=G-H	Recycled Waste Amount per day/ton	84	85	123	213	271	276
J=(I/G)*100%	Recycling Rate	5%	5%	7%	12%	15%	15%

Source: Author's elaboration based on the data ADB UZB-TA 8004

3. Methodology

3.1 Case study

As we learned from previous studies, ADB project's research was a significant source to realize the background of municipal solid waste management in Uzbekistan. However, there is still uncertainty concerning specific parts. Notably, the existing recycling system is not portrayed well. The only basic level of waste recycling available and many of them operate informally. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge the independent researches on this topic are limited. Also, it was already five years after the evaluation of the SWMIP. Therefore, we did our own case study to test the accuracy of that estimation and make a clear understanding of the current state of the recycling system in Tashkent. Also, to explore the core problems, which are interrupting to enhance the waste management. Through the field survey results, this paper studies the problems and challenges in waste recycling system in the city and gives targeted policy suggestions.

3.2 Survey

In this study to grasp the real situation of the existing recycling system in Tashkent, we have carried out a field survey in the period Aug 23 - Sep 18, 2017. The interviews of survey were conducted by the author Hilola Sul'tonova under the supervision of professor Hidetoshi Yamashita.

This case study is based on field survey and face to face interviews and has also synthetically used literature review, to obtain the primary results such as the flow amounts and direction of recyclable waste, influencing factors, recycling rates and so on. Following of the purpose of this study, we interviewed every kind of participants in the system, including social organizations, residents, scavengers, recycling markets employees and the managers of the process factories. However, making a question directly is not welcomed in this society. For this reason, the human network was precisely significant. Even the author is a citizen of Uzbekistan, and this research is related to her hometown; however, we needed to arrange the access through intermediaries.

We conducted semi-structured interviews at five recycling markets, three process factories and one waste collection point in the city. Interviews ranged from 30-60 minutes and collected both quantitative and qualitative information. To get quantitative information, we asked mainly about their working process, the sale prices for each type of recyclable waste, input and output amounts, price changes between the early introductory and current period. Furthermore, to obtain the qualitative information we also discussed with managers about their experienced problems in the past and present, the current interests and future goals in their business. All interviews were conducted in Uzbek language and recorded, transcribed and translated into English by the author.

In Tashkent formal and informal participants exist simultaneously in the recycling system. During the survey we tried to connect to the both formal and informal participants as possible.

Scavengers

Scavengers are engaged in the forefront of the collecting and selling of recyclable materials. They picked up the valuable things from trashcans. Meanwhile, some scavengers' work is done by dustmen and cleaners. They could get a lot of recyclable waste in their cleaning work in the communities, markets, enterprises, and institutions. The scavengers usually sell the recyclable waste to the recycling markets, which offered higher prices in their neighborhoods. Unfortunately, total number of

scavengers is uncertain. They are responsible for their profits and losses. Since they do not accept the government's management, they belong to the informal system in this field.

Recycling market

Recycling market is an essential participant. The most current waste recycling shops exist for the following identified fractions: paper, cardboard, PET, plastics (bags and sheets) and metal. Almost all of the recyclable materials selling and buying go through the recycling markets. The recycling markets buy the recyclable waste from scavengers and residents and sell them to the processing factories after some primary processing work like sorting of the plastics, disassembly of the waste machines packaging and compress of the waste paper. Recycling markets usually have settled recycling places, storage yards and transporting vehicles. They straightly sell recyclable wastes to the appropriate process factories. Most recycling markets are operated by informal entrepreneurs, and some of them belong to the private process factories. Recycling markets are all responsible for their profits and losses.

Process factories

The process factories remanufacture products using the recyclable waste. Most processing factories in Tashkent are regular production enterprises such as paper and plastics, while recyclable wastes are only part of their raw materials. Each plant accepts the specific type of recyclable waste. Usually, process factories produce an intermediate product or final product in several qualities. Thus, first of all, they are engaged in the sorting and initial processing according to the condition of materials. For instance, in a paper by its whiteness, in cardboard by thickness, in plastics sorted by types, cleanness and so on. This kind of sorting is necessary to get a different level of qualities. Conforming to the quality of their product, other entrepreneurs may purchase to use for various purposes. Moreover, the level of quality assigns its price. Most process factories have their several private recycling markets; they gather recyclables and deliver to the plants as a raw material.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Findings

Based on the interviews of recycling markets employees, we can note that about 70% of recyclable waste is brought through scavengers and traders from nearby local household bazaars and the other 30% passes directly to the recycling markets from residents. The recyclable waste recycled by scavengers account for the larger proportion. The interviews revealed that, the reason is many residents are reluctant to bring recyclable waste to recycling markets because of the time involved. The scavengers just have the effect of collecting and transporting the recyclable wastes.

After recycling markets, the recyclable wastes are directly sent to the process factories. This is mainly determined by the different recovery and re-use processes of different kinds of recyclable wastes. There are no separated sorting centers; usually, this function occurs in recycling shops in the case of plastics and metal. Because, the waste plastics and waste metal need to be classified and pre-processed before sending to the specific recovery factories; waste paper usually passes through the process factories.

We organized all obtained quantitative data as a result from recycling markets. First, we measured profitability of five recycling markets by surplus value and summarized. The prices and quantity for each type of waste were slightly different in each market, but we chose the average number for all in the table. We always asked minimum and maximum amount of purchased each type of recyclable waste during the whole year.

The information flow

The informal recycling system has been existing for a long time in Tashkent and established a relatively mature social relationship network to attract the recyclable wastes. However, the information flow of the existing recycling system was not enough to smooth, and related statistical data is not open-accessible. After the survey of existing literature and converse with government officers and ADB's Improvement of Solid Waste Management project staff, we realized that basic statistical micro data is not taking regularly in this field or the government is strict such stat info dissemination.

Therefore, our survey findings might be the first micro-level statistics among the recycling markets and process-recovery factories in Tashkent city.

The amount flow and directions

Figure 3 describes the structure of the existing recycling system in Tashkent. The recycling markets were the crucial links in this system.

Figure 3: MSW recycling process stages and system boundary

Source: Author’s elaboration based on the survey.

Based on the survey results, the average amount of the collected recyclable waste at each market was calculated about 1,6ton (=1,635kg) per day (Table 17). 1.6ton is a real micro data for August 2017. If there are 110 recycling markets in the whole system maximum, we estimate that the amount of the collected waste for recycling would be about 180 ton (=179,850 kg) per day (Table 17). Recycling markets handle these collected wastes directly to the process factories at the different price. However, there is no change in the flow amount. We may note that 180ton is the recycled waste amount per day in Tashkent. However, in the previous section’s ADB project research estimation shows recycled amount waste should be 276 ton per day for 2017. According to their estimation, each recycling market should collect recyclable wastes 2.5 ton per day. However, the gap between their estimation and our survey result were substantially different. For this reason, we cannot assume that waste recycling rate is 15% as they estimated for 2017.

Table 2: Recyclable materials collection for one recycling market in a day

Type	Price per kg	1 Recycling market per day		110 Recycling market per day	
		Quantity kg	Value	Quantity kg	Value
Paper	1,200	300	360,000	33,000	39,600,000
Cardboard	1,100	450	495,000	49,500	54,450,000
PET bottle	1,500	110	165,000	12,100	18,150,000
Plastics	1,000	75	75,000	8,250	8,250,000
Metal	400	700	280,000	77,000	30,800,000
Total		1,635	1,375,000	179,850	151,250,000

Source: Author's elaboration based on the field survey interviews in the recycling markets.

Also, survey interviews showed that in present existing recycling markets have demands only for paper, cardboard, PET bottles, plastics, and metal. If we sum the percentages of these items from Table 18, it is equal to 38%. Thus, we divide Table 18 into three groups like an organic waste, recyclable waste, and others (including all remained other compositions) in the Figure 4.

Figure 4: The average percentage of MSW in three main components

From the figure 4, we may note that existing recycling markets can accept only 38% of total MSW. If we use ADB's estimation data for 2017, total waste generation per day is 1,843 ton, and it is 38% is equal to 700.3 ton. However, currently, recycling markets collected waste amount is about 180 ton per day. Thus, we may estimate that 520.5ton recyclable materials are not recovering operatively. This vast difference shows that collection of the recyclable waste is not working efficiently. Most of the recyclable and recoverable materials are still going to the landfill sites.

Stakeholders' contribution to the current system

The stakeholders of waste management systems also were identified during the survey. The primary "recognized" or formal stakeholders included the local authority Hokimiyat, some ministries from central government and Maxsustrans providing collection services. These participants in the workshop acknowledged the local government as the most important stakeholders, which set up policies and the provision of solid waste management systems respectively. The private contractors are also regarded as essential stakeholders as well as the service users such as households, civil organizations such as mahallas, commercial and industrial sector. Less mentioned are educational and research institutions, political parties, health care centers, media, donor organizations, police and other leaders.

The "unrecognized" or informal stakeholders include scavengers collecting door to door, on the streets or in the collection points, itinerant waste buyers, recycling markets owners and street sweepers.

At present, however, “unrecognized” stakeholders’ contributions are limited by the absence of government policies to encourage reuse and recycling. Scavengers are not integrated into the recycling chain. Only a limited amount of recyclable and valuable waste is collected and recovered.

Seasoning issue

Also, in the interviews, the managers mentioned that there occurs the seasoning problem in the process-recovery factories. There is lack of waste source material, especially in the winter days. Because of scavengers actions are passive in cold weather and unsteady for the whole year. We found that not only scavengers’ movement is low in the winter. However, also total waste volume is less than the summer season. A seasonal variation in waste volumes of approximately 25% occurs between summer and winter. (World Bank Report №. PIC5014, 1997, p.5)

However, the activities of scavengers could have a high impact on the economy and waste management if the scavengers were adequately organized, enlightened, and provided with necessary economic and institutional support. We consider that with the proper education and campaign programs, recycling could be enhanced in the country.

By improving the education level of the recycling practitioners, the government could organize the training activities for them, providing them with the professional recycling knowledge, such as the standard classification and processing method of different recyclable waste types, the laws, and regulations in recycling business and development plans of the recycling system.

Social issue

Public interest and attitude is a key element in the success of recycling system. However, within Tashkent, the municipality has shown, so far, no organization or strategic planning for the start of the formal recycling system. The municipality will need to offer citizens a mechanism for sorting and recycling by implementing collection or bring the system. What are obvious in this region are lack of knowledge on the public’s side and the lack of action by the municipality for implementing MSW recycling.

4.2 Shortcomings

We are aware that our research may have limitations. A lack of municipal solid waste microeconomic data provided by national statistics committee. For this reason, we tried to use data provided by the ADB Solid waste management improvement project in Tashkent.

However, this project's data is limited and their actual data if only for 2012. To our best knowledge, project's source materials do not offer any information about recyclable waste collection depots and recovery factories. Moreover, there is no permanent environmental monitoring to measure related indicators.

We tried to examine and determine the current recycling practices in the city and its core problems, which are interrupting to enhance the waste management. Nonetheless, our survey analysis also based on limited numbers of the raw semi-interviews results. Further data collection is required to estimate the current state of waste management in Tashkent briefly.

5. Conclusion

The study investigated the municipal solid waste management challenges in Uzbekistan and its current core problems, which interrupt to enhance the recycling practices in Tashkent city.

As we learned from previous sections, solid waste management is a multi-dimensional issue. Municipalities, in general, seek for equipment as a path to find solutions to the diversity of problems they face. However, this study shows that an efficient system is not only based in technological solutions but also environmental, socio-cultural, legal, institutional and economic linkages that should be present to enable the overall system to function.

Moreover, waste management involves a large number of different stakeholders, with various fields of interest. Every participant plays a role in shaping the system of a city. However, it is seen only as a responsibility of the local authorities. In the best of the cases, the citizens are considered co-responsible together with the municipality. Detailed understandings on who are the stakeholders and the responsibilities they have in the structure are important steps to establish an efficient and effective system.

Communication transfer between the different stakeholders is of high importance in order to get a well-functioning waste management system in the city in developing countries.

Also, fundamental is to produce reliable data and to create proper information channels within and between municipalities. Decision makers, responsible for planning and policy-making, need to be well informed about the situation of the cities to make change for the positive side, developing integrated waste management strategies adapted to the needs of the people considering their ability to pay for the services.

Recycling should be integrated with municipal solid waste management options to decrease urban environmental degradation. It can be achieved through promotion of economically efficient and environmentally sound practices in managing municipal waste. Recycling might be promoted by the encouraging separation at the source. Separation at the source can be accomplished through financial incentives stimulation, legislation and rising of environmental awareness.

Furthermore, universities, research centers and centers of excellence have a significant role in preparing professionals and technicians in environmental fields, including waste management. Research institutions should contribute in developing the field of waste management. Many developing countries have already seen the positive effects of investing in education and research by having cleaner cities, citizens assuming their responsibilities and higher status of solid waste workers.

The informative data provided about the factors influencing solid waste management systems might be useful for other individual or organization interested in planning, changing or implementing a waste management system in a city. However, in Uzbekistan, the physical datasets related to the waste management and material flow under the current national statistical framework is not well developed. Thus, in the future research, more efforts should be devoted to the investigation of more apparent statistical data and waste cycling scene.

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